

OXIDATION INDUCED SHRINKAGE AND STRESS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS AT HIGH TEMPERATURES: NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

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SUMMARY

In the present paper the thermo oxidation induced shrinkage and stress in carbon fibre reinforced polymers at high temperatures are simulated by a numerical multiphysical coupled model implemented within the ABAQUS commercial finite element code; the shrinkage profiles are experimentally measured through confocal interferometric microscopy and compared successfully to numerical predictions.

Keywords: thermo oxidation, high temperatures, chemical shrinkage, multiphysical modelling, interferometric microscopy

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are nowadays largely employed in aircraft industries due to their contribution to structure weight and cost reduction, good fatigue performance and relatively low maintenance cost. The weight gain attained by the employment of composite materials in aircraft composite structure can be as high as 30% (up to 55% for helicopter parts made by aramid/epoxy composites). In view of an optimal use of composite materials in aircraft structures new applications are foreseen, for instance the employment of such materials for parts which are highly exposed to aggressive environments where temperatures can be as high as 150 – 180°C and in which the presence of oxygen and thermo oxidative phenomena may lead to accelerated ageing phenomena. Full understanding of thermo oxidative phenomena needs the employment of strongly coupled experimental and theoretical methods due to the interaction of phenomena which classically pertain to different research domain (physics, chemistry, mechanics ...). Thermo oxidation in composite materials makes the object of several research studies since almost 10 years [1-4]; in particular it has been shown experimentally [3] that oxidising environments contribute to the onset and the development of damage much more than neutral ones (see figure 1). From the chemistry point of view, thermo oxidation consists in a coupled mechanism of oxygen diffusion within the matter and thermally activated chemical reactions of the oxidising species with the epoxy network leading to chain disruption of the macromolecular network [5] and mass loss due to the departure of volatile species; for the epoxy network this in turn

leads, respectively, to stiffness and strength loss and chemical shrinkage which is responsible for strain, stress and possibly damage development within the composite.

Figure 1: SEM pictures of carbon epoxy samples aged at 150°C in (a) neutral and (b-c) oxidising environments.

Today, the chemical phenomenon is relatively well known and firmly established in the literature, despite the approaches are sometimes formally different. On the other hand, the mechanical phenomena following the chemistry are less known and need further understanding: in particular the mechanisms responsible for damage onset and propagation are far to be understood both at the experimental and the theoretical level.

The present paper focuses on the effects of thermo oxidation on the development of strain and stress in composite materials at the microscopic scale, that is, at the scale of the elementary constituents, fibres and polymer matrix.

Thermo oxidation induced shrinkage profiles are measured by confocal interferometric microscopy on the side surfaces of CFRP IM7/977-2 composites aged under neutral and oxidising environments. These measures show that the depth of such profiles increases as the distance between fibres increases, that is, as the size of the resin rich zones inside the composite increases.

Numerical simulations are based on a multiphysical coupled model developed within the framework on the thermodynamics of irreversible processes [6] and implemented within the ABAQUS commercial finite element code [7] via the user subroutines.

Starting from the experimental measurements a local scale FE model has been built and employed for numerical simulations. A good agreement between experimental measurements and model simulations has been found for composite samples aged at 150°C under atmospheric air for 192h: once validated, the model has been employed for

the simulation of stress close to the fibre/matrix interfaces and for the evaluation of the conditions of damage onset.

EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS

All samples (pure resin and composite samples) were oxidised 192h at 150°C under atmospheric air in dedicated climatic chambers (“COMEDI” chambers) opportunely conceived for such applications. Figure 2 shows a view of a COMEDI climatic chamber and some details of the sample fixation system.

Figure 2: (a) View of the “COMEDI” climatic chamber (closed) (b) some details of the chamber (open) and of the sample fixation system.

Thermo oxidation induced changes in mechanical properties (local stiffness) have been measured in oxidised pure resin samples by ultra micro indentation; this technique is able to characterise with good accuracy the strong gradients which are present in small portions of material after oxidation. The measured elastic indentation moduli (EIT) and their profiles have been then correlated with the results of the thermo oxidation coupled numerical equations (eq. 7) as detailed later.

The thermo oxidation induced shrinkage profiles have been measured by confocal interferometric microscopy on the side surfaces of CFRP IM7/977-2 carbon-epoxy samples cut from $[+45_2/-45_4/+45_2/0_{10}/90_{10}]_s$ composite plates. The microscope employed for the shrinkage profile measurements is a Taylor Hobson TALYSURF CCI 6000, whose measure technique is based on Michelson interferometry; with a 50x magnification, this apparatus is able to extract 3D images and profiles with a vertical resolution up to 10^{-5} μm along a $0.35 \times 0.35 \text{ mm}^2$ surface. Values of slopes higher than 27° cannot be measured by the apparatus and are reported as unmeasured points. Figure 3 illustrates a typical image (observed at room temperature) captured by the apparatus at the side surface edges (exposed to the environment) of an oxidised composite sample (aged at 150°C).

Figure 3: Example of images extracted by confocal interferometric microscopy at the exposed side edge surfaces of an oxidised composite sample.

The illustration shows the presence of matrix and fibre rich zones within the composite together with a certain amount of unmeasured points. By analogy with SEM clichés obtained on the same samples zones containing a concentration of unmeasured points have been correlated to matrix microcracks, flaws and fibre/matrix debondings.

Figure 4: Example of thermo oxidation induced matrix shrinkage between two constraining consecutive fibres.

Thermo oxidation induced shrinkage has been qualitatively and quantitatively characterised as a function of the fibre-to-fibre distance by extracting and post-processing a certain number of profiles such as that illustrated in figure 4. This figure shows that the fibres are not all at the same height due to natural variability of the

composite and that a proper definition for the reference height is needed in order to perform correct measurements. In this study the average height between two consecutive fibres has been taken as the reference height.

COUPLED THERMO CHEMO MECHANICAL MODEL

The composite is modelled as a two phase material: fibres, which are thermally and chemically stable with respect to oxidation, and resin polymer matrix in which the ageing process takes place. The fibre/matrix interfaces are not modelled. The model has been developed within the framework of the thermodynamics of irreversible processes [6] following a deterministic approach and with little use of phenomenological relationships. In order to describe in full detail the chemical processes which take place during thermo oxidation, the model fully integrates a chemical mechanistic scheme developed by Colin et al. [1], which allows to determine the evolution of each chemical species locally and at all time during the process, taking into account reaction diffusion couplings. The evolution equations of species concentrations are thus given by the following system of differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial [O_2]}{\partial t} &= -k_2 [P^\circ] [O_2] + k_6 [PO_2^\circ]^2 + D_{O_2} \nabla^2 [O_2] \\
\frac{d[POOH]}{dt} &= k_3 [PH] [PO_2^\circ] - k_1 [POOH] \\
\frac{d[PH]}{dt} &= -k_3 [PH] [PO_2^\circ] - \gamma k_1 [POOH] \\
\frac{d[PO_2^\circ]}{dt} &= k_2 [P^\circ] [O_2] - k_3 [PH] [PO_2^\circ] - k_5 [PO_2^\circ] [P^\circ] - 2 k_6 [PO_2^\circ]^2 \\
\frac{d[P]}{dt} &= 2k_1 [POOH] - k_2 [P^\circ] [O_2] + k_3 [PH] [PO_2^\circ] - 2k_4 [P^\circ]^2 - k_5 [PO_2^\circ] [P^\circ] \quad (\text{eq. 1})
\end{aligned}$$

in which k_1 to k_6 are the parameters of the chemical reaction, D_{O_2} is the oxygen diffusion coefficient. The full mechanistic scheme identifies several different chemical species: $POOH$, PH , O_2 , P° , PO_2° (the symbol $^\circ$ represents free radicals), H_2O , volatiles V , and three species of non reacting products. Volatiles are supposed to have an extremely high speed of diffusion and are chemically neutral. The first equation of (1) gives the local evolution of the oxygen concentration within the polymer (noted $[O_2]$), due to both the chemical reaction and the species diffusion. The system (1) can be solved numerically by specifying the appropriate initial and boundary conditions. In particular on the free edges exposed to the environment the oxygen concentration is supposed to follow the Henry law. Oxygen reaction diffusion is normally characterised by a global parameter, the concentration of oxidation products, defined by:

$$Q(x, y, z, t) = \int_0^t \frac{d[O_2]}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

The thermo oxidation induced shrinkage strain tensor is calculated starting from the local advancement of the chemical reaction and is given by [8]:

$$\mathbf{E}^{SH} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\Delta m}{m} - \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho_0} \right) \mathbf{I}, \quad \frac{1}{m_0} \frac{dm}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho_0} \left(M_{O_2} \frac{d[O_2]}{dt} - M_{H_2O} \frac{d[H_2O]}{dt} - M_v \frac{d[V]}{dt} \right) \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor, m and ρ respectively the mass and the density of the material at time t , the index “0” indicates the same variables at the start time, and M_X the molar mass of the component X . From the point of view of mechanics, the resin follows a nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive law, described by a model similar to that proposed by Cunaat [9]:

$$Tr \mathbf{S} = 3K_V tr \mathbf{E} - 3K_V \mathbf{E}^{TH} - 3K_V \mathbf{E}^{SH} - 3 \sum_{j=1}^n K_j z_j^{trE}$$

$$\mathbf{S}^d = 2G_V \mathbf{E}^d - 2 \sum_{j=1}^m G_j \mathbf{Z}_j^{Ed} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

with:

$$K_j = p_j^K K_R \quad \text{and} \quad G_j = p_j^G G_R$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n p_j^K = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{j=1}^m p_j^G = 1 \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

in which \mathbf{S} is the stress tensor, \mathbf{E} the strain tensor, the index “ d ” refers to the deviatoric part of the corresponding tensor and \mathbf{E}^{TH} is the free thermal strain tensor. The “ j ” internal variables which rule the viscoelastic behaviour are noted by z_j^{trE} and \mathbf{Z}_j^{Ed} (spherical and deviatoric part, respectively). Fifty variables are taken into account, each with its own relaxation time, τ_j^{trE} and τ_j^{Ed} , respectively. The weights p_j^K and p_j^G of the distribution associated to each characteristic time follow a law close to that proposed by Cunaat [9]. The internal variables are ruled by differential equations of the type:

$$\frac{d z_j^{trE}}{dt} = \frac{1}{a_s(T) \tau_j^{trE}} (z_j^{trE} - z_{\infty}^{trE})$$

$$\frac{d \mathbf{Z}_j^{Ed}}{dt} = \frac{1}{a_d(T) \tau_j^{Ed}} (\mathbf{Z}_j^{Ed} - \mathbf{Z}_{\infty}^{Ed}) \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

The parameters of the model are: the glass and relaxed moduli of the resin, K_V , K_R , G_V , G_R , a coefficient of the distribution law (not detailed here) and the functions $a_s(T)$ et $a_d(T)$. The model has been identified by relaxation traction tests at 150°C performed on unoxidised pure resin samples. In this model, thermo mechanics couplings are represented by the free thermal strain tensor term depending on the free expansion of the resin and by the functions $a_s(T)$ et $a_d(T)$. Chemo mechanics couplings are taken into account by the thermo oxidation induced shrinkage strain tensor, \mathbf{E}^{SH} , calculated by eq. 2. Besides the thermo viscoelastic behaviour of the resin, the model integrates also the expression of the local indentation modulus (EIT) of the resin as a function of the concentration of oxygen products, eq. 7, identified by UMI tests, as detailed later. The model has been implemented into the ABAQUS finite element commercial code via the available user subroutines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows the elastic indentation modulus (EIT) as a function of the concentration of oxidation products Q for a pure resin sample aged 100h, 600h and 1000h at 150°C under atmospheric air. The phenomenological law relating the resin modulus as a function of the concentration of oxidation products is thus obtained, by regression:

$$EIT = 5510 - 1469 e^{-0.48Q} \quad (\text{eq. 7})$$

Figure 5: Elastic indentation modulus (EIT) as a function of the concentration of oxidation products.

Shrinkage profiles have been measured in virgin (unoxidised) and oxidised composite samples aged 192h under atmospheric air at 150°C. Measurements have been performed in two distinct characteristic zones: intraply zones (fibre-to-fibre distance < 50µm), characterized by closed loop resin rich zones and interply zones (fibre-to-fibre distance > 50µm), matrix rich pockets between adjacent plies, characterized by open loop contours. Figure 6 shows the measured maximum shrinkage depth as a function of the fibre-to-fibre distance for virgin and oxidized samples.

Figure 6: Maximum shrinkage depth as a function of the fibre-to-fibre distance in virgin and oxidised composite samples.

In both samples and in both zones (intraply and interply zones) the maximum shrinkage depth increases by increasing the fibre-to-fibre distance, that is, the size of the resin rich zone. The maximum shrinkage depth is systematically higher in oxidized samples than in unoxidised ones, due to the substantial contribution of the thermo oxidation chemical shrinkage. Figure 7 shows a comparison between the measured and the numerically simulated maximum shrinkage depth for a sample aged 192h at 150°C under atmospheric air: for such an environmental condition the two curves are in very good agreement.

Figure 7: Comparison between measured and numerically simulated maximum shrinkage depth as a function of the fibre-to-fibre distance in oxidised samples.

Once validated, the model can be employed for the simulation of thermo oxidation induced stress field close to the fibre/matrix interface. Simulations have been performed for a composite sample exposed 48h under neutral environment, N_2 at 150°C, and for a sample exposed 48h under a particularly aggressive environment, 5 bars O_2 at 150°C. At the fibre/matrix interface some components of the stress tensor become singular as soon as the free edge is approached. Thus the stress solution is strongly dependent on the adopted numerical mesh. However, despite the presence of the singularity, for a same mesh, thermo oxidative environments engender strain and stress conditions which are severe if compared to the same conditions under neutral environments; in particular the average value of the Von Mises stress calculated for samples under a thermo oxidative environment is 91% higher than the same stress calculated under neutral environments (71.5 MPa and 37,5 MPa, respectively). This shows that the contribution of the chemistry to the development of mechanical strain and stress is substantial and

may lead to the establishment of critical conditions and to damage onset and propagation.

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

In the present paper the effects of thermo oxidation on the development of strain and stress at the microscopic scale have been carried out.

Thermo oxidation induced shrinkage profiles have been measured by confocal interferometric microscopy on the side surfaces of CFRP IM7/977-2 composites aged under neutral and oxidising environments. These measures show that the depth of such profiles increases as the distance between fibres increases, that is, as the size of the resin rich zones inside the composite increases.

Numerical simulations based on a multiphysical coupled model have been developed within the framework on the thermodynamics of irreversible processes and implemented within the ABAQUS commercial finite element code.

A good agreement between measured and simulated thermo oxidation shrinkage profiles has been found for composite samples aged at 150°C under atmospheric air for 192h: once validated, the model has been employed for the simulation of stress close to the fibre/matrix interfaces, showing that thermo oxidative environments are much more aggressive than neutral ones and possibly responsible for damage onset. The conditions of damage onset and propagation deserve to be better investigated and will be the object of future studies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present study has been carried out within the framework of the COMEDI research program, funded by the French ANR RNMP agency. All partners of the research, LIM ENSAM Paris and EADS IW Suresnes are gratefully acknowledged. Noel Brunetiere and the Laboratoire de Mécanique du Solide of the University of Poitiers are also acknowledged for their help in performing the confocal interferometric microscopy measurements.

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